

A Review On Artificial Intelligence In Drug Discovery And Development

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ABSTRACT: Recently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has begun to be applied in a number of societal sectors, with the pharmaceutical sector leading the way. This review emphasizes the significant application of AI in a variety of pharmaceutical sectors, including drug development and discovery, drug repurposing, pharmaceutical productivity enhancement, clinical trials, etc to mention a few. This reduces the human workload and helps to meet goals quickly. There is also discussion of crosstalk regarding the methods and instruments used to enforce AI, ongoing difficulties and solutions, and the prospects of AI in the pharmaceutical sectors.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence, Drug development, Drug discovery, Machine learning.

➤ INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry has increased the digitalization of data in recent years. However, the task of collecting, evaluating, and applying that data to address complex clinical problems is presented by this digitalization breakthrough [1]. The adoption of AI is fueled by this need since it can better automate the management of large volumes of data [2]. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology-driven system that includes a variety of advanced tools and networks intended to mimic human intelligence. However, the necessity of human bodily presence is not entirely threatened by it [3, 4]. AI uses software and systems that can analyze and learn from input data to make decisions on their own that are intended to accomplish particular objectives. As this review explains, its applications in the pharmaceutical industry are always growing. According to the McKinsey Global Institute, the rapid developments in AI-driven automation are probably going to completely change how people work in society [5, 6].

AI: Networks and Tools - Machine learning (ML) is a fundamental technique in artificial intelligence (AI), which includes a number of methodological domains such as reasoning, information representation, and solution finding. Algorithms that can spot patterns in categorized data are used in machine learning. Deep learning (DL), a subfield of machine learning, makes use of artificial neural networks (ANNs). The 'perceptrons,' which resemble real neurons in humans and replicate the transmission of electrical signals in the brain, are among the interconnected sophisticated computer units that make up these networks [7]. ANNs are made up of a collection of nodes that receive distinct inputs and, using algorithms to solve issues, convert them into output either singly or in combination [8]. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and multilayer perceptron (MLP) networks are a number of the different forms of artificial neural networks (ANNs) that use both supervised or unsupervised training processes [9,10]. Applications for MLP networks can be found in fields including control systems, process identification, pattern recognition, and optimization support. Usually, supervised learning techniques that can act as universal pattern classifiers and only work in one direction are used to train it [11]. Boltzmann constants and Hopfield networks are examples of RNNs, which are networks containing feedback loops that may store and retrieve information [11,12]. CNNs are used in image and video processing, biological

system modelling, processing complex brain processes, pattern recognition, and advanced signal processing. They are made up of dynamic systems with local connections that are characterized by their topology [13]. Kohonen, adaptive linear element (ADALINE), learning vector quantization (LVQ), radial basis function (RBF), and counter-propagation networks are more complex varieties [9, 11]. The AI approach domains are summarized in Figure 1.

The networks that make up the essential structure of AI systems have served as the basis for the development of several technologies. The AI-powered IBM Watson supercomputer (IBM, New York, USA) is one example of such a tool. It was created to help analyze a patient's medical records and compare them with a large database in order to provide cancer treatment plans. As seen by its capacity to detect breast cancer in 60 seconds, this technology may also detect disorders swiftly [14, 15].

FIGURE 1 – Technique Domains of AI.

➤ *Role of Artificial Intelligence in Different Phases of Drug Products Development and Lifecycle Management*

Performance as well as accuracy could be greatly increased by incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the pharmaceutical development process at every stage, from preliminary research to clinical use [16]. AI helps with evidence-based decision-making, rational medication design, personalized medicine, and the management and analysis of clinical data for future drug development. It also helps discover the best treatments for particular patients [17]. E-VAI, an AI-powered analytical and decision support platform designed by the company Eularis, is a super instance of this type of implementation. E-VAI analyzes data on rivals, significant partners, and customer share to develop analytical strategies using algorithms for machine learning in a simple-to-use format. This makes it possible to determine the main factors influencing sales in the pharmaceutical industry [18]. As a result, it helps marketing professionals forecast lucrative investing sectors, improve underperforming sales, and allocate resources strategically. The different applications of AI in drug discovery and development are summarized in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 – Applications of AI in different subfields of the pharmaceutical sector, from drug discovery to pharmaceutical product management.

➤ *AI in Drug Discovery*

Numerous pharmacologically active molecules can be synthesized thanks to the large chemical space, which is thought to contain around 1060 potential compounds. But historically, the lack of cutting-edge technologies has slowed down the medication development process, making it expensive and time-consuming [19]. Artificial intelligence (AI), which makes it possible to identify hit and lead compounds, faster target validation, and improved pharmaceutical design analysis, is capable of being used to efficiently decrease this difficulty [20]. While artificial intelligence has various applications in drug discovery, there are still major issues related to data, particularly uncertainty, diversity, and amount of data. Traditional computing methods are often inadequate for analyzing the large datasets necessary in pharmaceutical research – large datasets that may be on the order of millions of chemical structures.

Factors may be easily and faithfully calculated, such as basic physicochemical variables like log P and log D, with the application of quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models, but QSAR models struggle to accurately develop complex biological endpoints like toxicity and bioactivity. Furthermore, QSAR-based modelling has problems of limited validation, experimental error, and from small training datasets. To overcome these limitations, modern artificial intelligence (AI) methods, especially deep learning (DL), have been implemented for evaluating drug candidates for safety and efficacy using big data analytics. For example, in evaluating a data set of 15 drug candidates related to ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity), DL models produced superior predicted accuracy compared to classical machine learning models during the 2012 Merck QSAR ML competition [21, 22].

The concept of virtual chemical space, which is akin to a molecular "map," provides the ability to visualize and explore molecular characteristics to identify potential bioactive molecules. Virtual screening (VS) methods, using both structure-based and ligand-based approaches, help identify and eliminate unsuitable molecules at an early point, reducing the amount of wasted resources. For these types of in silico screening programs, public databases (e.g., PubChem, ChemBank, DrugBank, ChemDB) offer invaluable resources. Additionally, the development of drug methodologies that utilize biological fingerprints and Coulomb matrices discuss the physical, chemical, and toxicological properties of potential leads [23]. AI-driven models combine prediction modelling and chemical similarity, as well as virtual simulation to forecast target–compound interactions [20, 21]. For instance, Pereira et al. developed and tested DeepVS, a new docking approach, on 40 receptors & 2,950 ligands that performed fairly well, even when compared with 95,000 decoy molecules [24].

A multi-objective automated replacement approach was used to improve cyclin-dependent kinase-2 inhibitors by exploring structural similarity, biochemical activity, and physical characteristics [25]. The introduction of AI-based QSAR models (for example, decision trees, support vector machines (SVM), random forests, and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) has also expedited and improved QSAR analysis [26, 27, 28]. King et al. compared six algorithms from AI to classify compounds based on biological activity and identified minimal statistical differences compared to typical methods. However, the study demonstrates that there are opportunities for AI to enhance drug discovery and development initiatives through greater accuracy, speed, and scale [29].

AI in Drug Screening

Before selecting a candidate to proceed with clinical trials, drug screening is the process used to find and enhance possible treatments. Large chemical libraries could be screened for a particular biological function using its high-throughput screening assays, which could be time-consuming. Artificial intelligence (AI) has the implicit to transform drug testing through improving the search for new medications while decreasing the time and cost involved in drug development. One application of AI is drug testing involves machine learning techniques, that are capable of analyzing large amounts of data from a number of sources, like biological and molecular data, clinical trial outcomes, and scholarly publications. These algorithms can assist in determining which drug ideas are most likely to be successful by patterns of detection and relate to human being's research might have overlooked. AI also utilizes virtual screening, which measures the effectiveness of possible medications using virtual reality. AI can also enhance the speed of clinical trials by determining which patients will respond to one or another medicine first [32].

AI in Drug Design

The design of drugs is the method to create fresh medications and improve medicines that already exist to cure illnesses. In order to find compounds that can interact with particular biological targets, like enzymes or receptors, and have a therapeutic effect, computer models, simulations, and experiments are used. One of the basic issues that might be asked during the process of creating drugs can the chemical compounds result in the essential property profile. Using a computational model rooted in the quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR), a variety of chemicals or simple physicochemical properties, such as log P or log D, can be quickly estimated. Owing to its ability to predict structures of target proteins and interaction with drug molecules, artificial intelligence (AI) aids in drug molecule design. By forecasting the 3D protein structure, artificial intelligence (AI) can support drug discovery based on structures since the design complies with the target protein site's chemical environment. This would enable the prediction of a compound's effect on a target. AlphaFold serves as an illustration of this. By calculating the distance between neighboring amino acids and the matching angles of the peptide bonds, it forecasts the target protein's three-dimensional structure. Drug-protein interactions have a major role in a therapy's efficacy. Therapeutic efficacy has grown due to the accuracy of ligand-protein interactions anticipated by different AI approaches [30, 20].

AI in Drug Repurposing

The process of developing new uses for medications that have already been approved for human use is known as drug repurposing. By spotting novel therapeutic symptoms and possible drug combinations that humans would look out for using artificial intelligence (AI) may be able to speed up and improve the drug repurposing process. AI algorithms are capable of analyzing gene expression datasets in order to identify potential therapeutic targets for a particular disease and can even search databases that contain known drugs for possible compounds to treat a given disorder. Each time a clinical trial is undertaken, AI (artificial intelligence) systems can evaluate large datasets of clinical trial information and identify trends demonstrating how the drug may behave differently in multiple patient cohorts compared to the initial trial population. So, drug doses and treatment regimens can be counted on to be improved while identifying

possible safety signals for drugs being evaluated. AI techniques might be more helpful in identifying possible repurposing targets [31].

FIGURE 3 – AI in Drug Repurposing.

➤ *AI in designing drug molecules*

Prediction of the target protein

Choosing the right therapeutic target during drug development is essential for effective patient therapy. When creating a new therapeutic molecule, it is essential to accurately predict the target protein's structure because overexpression of particular proteins is linked to a number of disorders. By providing 3D protein structure prediction, artificial intelligence (AI) facilitates structure-based drug design by guaranteeing that the created compound conforms to the target interaction site's biological environment. This method aids in assessing a medication's safety and effectiveness prior to its real synthesis or manufacturing [33]. One well-known AI system, AlphaFold, analyzes polypeptide bonds and interaction distance in predicting 3D protein structures using deep neural networks (DNNs). With 25 out of 43 protein structures properly predicted, the model demonstrated remarkable accuracy. Similarly, Qureshi's study used a Recurrent Geometric Network (RGN) model to utilize recurrent neural networks (RNNs) for protein structure prediction. The protein sequence is encoded, and torsion angles and partially constructed geometric frameworks are employed as inputs to produce a refined 3D structure the result in the three stages of this process: computing, geometry, and estimate. The last step of the model produced a 3D structure of a protein, which was measured using the root mean square deviation (dRMSD) to compare the predicted structure to the experimentally determined structure, with RGN optimized with dRMSD as a loss function to realize better predictions [34].

Al Qurashi suggested his AI-based approach could produce protein structures faster than AlphaFold. Still, AlphaFold is more accurate overall, even while relying on sequences that are more similar to well-characterized protein structures to produce superior predictions [35]. A nonlinear triple neural network (NN) model was proposed to predict 2D protein structures using forward leaning and backpropagation error training in MATLAB. Input and output datasets were trained in MATLAB, using NN to learn the model and measure performance. This model obtained an overall prediction accuracy of 62.72% [36].

Prediction of drug-protein interaction

Drug-protein interactions play a crucial role in the mechanism of drug action, contributing to drug repurposing and polypharmacology optimization [33]. Through the more sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) techniques allow predictions about drug-protein interactions to be made with more clarity, such as Wang et al [33, 37]. (2022), who developed an SVM model to study a data set with more than 15,000 drug-protein interactions [38]. Also, Yu et al. (2022) developed random forest (RF) models that even corroborated integrating pharmacological and chemical types of data to predict drug-protein interactions that could be incorporated into drug development. Then, with predictive modelling, Xiao et al. (2023) bettered the results of the previous study. Finally, these AI techniques might provide an opportunity to repurpose approved drugs while minimizing costs associated with drug development for new drug treatments [39, 40]. Logistic regression and machine learning (ML) techniques will also be used to develop drug reuse strategies [41]. Drug design de novo has been a roadblock to the pharmaceutical industry, but using other AI strategies in new configurations to develop other fields employing AI to optimize synthetic paths or predict bioactivity present promise. Improvements in the pharmaceutical industry can be predicted in general [42, 43].

AI in advancing pharmaceutical product development

The identification of a new drug molecule will necessitate its incorporation into an appropriate dosage form with the desired delivery characteristics. In this regard, Artificial intelligence can be hosted on computational platforms that will eliminate the need for the previous trial and error approaches [47]. There are many computational tools that can solve problems associated with the design of formulations, such as stability, dissolution, porosity, and others, through the assistance of quantitative structure activity relationships (QSAR) [48]. Decision support tools utilize rule-based approaches to determine the type, nature, and amount of the excipients, depending on the physicochemical properties of the drug, and operate with feedback incorporated to oversee the process and intermediately adjust the process as needed [49].

Guo et al. combined Expert Systems (ES) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) in a hybrid system to develop direct-filling hard gelatine capsules of piroxicam according to the dictated specifications of its dissolution profile. The MODEL EXPERT SYSTEM (MES) uses input parameters to make formulations and recommendations for the development of the formulation. ANN uses back-propagation learning for linking formulation parameters to the desired response, with both being overseen by the control module, which is intended to assist with hassle-free formulation development [47]. Different mathematical methods, including computational fluid dynamics (CFD), discrete element modelling (DEM), and the finite element method, have been employed to assess the impact of the flow property of the powder on the die-filling and tablet compression process [50, 51]. CFD can also be employed to analyze the effect of tablet geometry on its dissolution profile [52]. In conjunction with AI, these mathematical models may significantly assist in the rapid production of pharmaceutical products.

➤ *Artificial Intelligence in Polypharmacology*

Drug molecules interactions with different targets to potentially interfere with one or more disease pathways are the subject of polypharmacology. It involves much more than just focusing on one protein. It calls for a deeper comprehension of the medications structure-activity relationship. Drug development requires processing vast amounts of data, and AI can reveal polypharmacological interactions between ligand binding to numerous targets using a variety of similarity-based, network-based, and structural methodologies. The application of AI for polypharmacology modeling is expected to accelerate drug discovery for disorders of the central nervous system and cancer [31].

FIGURE 4 – AI in Polypharmacology.

➤ *AI in clinical trial design*

To ascertain if a medication is safe and effective for a particular ailment, clinical trials require an important financial commitment and take six to seven years. Nevertheless, the business suffers substantial losses because only one out of ten compounds used in these procedures is approved [44]. These failures could be brought on by inadequate infrastructure, a lack of technological requirements, and poor patient selection. However, artificial intelligence can help decrease these mistakes because of the vast amount of digital medical data that is available [45]. Thirty percent of clinical study failures are due to clinical dropout, which necessitates extra recruitment to conclude the trial, wasting both time and money. By closely observing patients and assisting them in following the clinical trial procedure, this can be prevented [46]. In a phase II experiment, Ai Cure developed mobile software to monitor individuals who have schizophrenia's consistent medication use. This enhanced patient adherence by 25%, guaranteeing the clinical trial's safe conclusion.

FIGURE 5 – AI in Clinical Trials.

➤ *Pharmaceutical market of AI*

Pharmaceutical companies are turning to AI in an effort to decrease the financial expenses and failure rates associated with VS. The AI market grew from US\$200 million in 2015 to US\$700 million in 2018, and by 2024, it appears to reach \$5 billion [53]. AI is predicted to transform the pharmaceutical and medical industries by 40% between 2017 and 2024. Numerous pharmaceutical corporations have invested in artificial intelligence (AI) and continue to perform so. They have partnered with AI organizations to build

crucial technology in the field of healthcare. For instance, The Royal Free London NHS Foundation Trust worked with DeepMind Technologies, a Google company, to assist in acute kidney injury.

➤ *Ongoing challenges in espousing AI: leads on ways to overcome*

Since these data are utilized for the system's subsequent training, the availability of a significant volume of data is essential to AI's overall effectiveness. A business may have to pay more to get data from several database providers, and the data must be high-quality and dependable to guarantee accurate result prediction. The pharmaceutical industry faces other obstacles to the full-fledged adoption of AI, such as a lack of skilled workers to operate AI-based platforms, small businesses' limited budgets, concerns about job loss due to human replacement, skepticism about AI-generated data, and the "black box" phenomenon, which refers to how the AI platform draws its conclusions [6]. With time, some jobs in clinical trials, manufacturing, supply chains, medication research, and sales will be automated; nevertheless, these all fall under the category of "narrow AI," where AI must be trained using a significant amount of data in order to be appropriate for a given task.

Therefore, for the AI platform to be developed, implemented, and run successfully, human intervention is required. However, while AI is now replacing repetitive duties, the fear of unemployment may not be real. Instead, human intelligence can be utilized to produce more complex insights and creative ideas. However, a number of drug manufacturers have embraced AI, and it is expected that by 2022, the pharmaceutical industry will generate US\$2.199 billion in revenues from AI-based solutions, with an investment of over US\$7.20 billion across more than 300 deals between 2013 and 2018 [54]. Pharmaceutical companies require clarification on the possibility of AI technology in solving problems after it has been utilized in usage, as well as knowledge of the realistic objectives that can be met. To fully capitalize on the AI system, skilled data scientists and software engineers with a solid understanding of AI technology, as well as a firm grasp of the organization's company target and R&D goal, can be established.

➤ *Advantage of AI technology*

The following are a few potential advantages of AI technology: [20, 43, 55]

- i) Reduce Errors: Artificial intelligence (AI) reduces errors and improves accuracy. Intelligent robots are deployed to discover space because they are composed of strong metal bodies and can survive the adverse environment of space.
- ii) Hard exploration: Exploration can benefit from AI. Searching for fuel is another purpose for it. AI systems can overcome human faults by exploring the Ookean. Everyday application: AI is incredibly helpful in our day-to-day tasks. The GPS system, for instance, is frequently utilized for lengthy trips. Robots with artificial intelligence installed anticipate what a user will input. Typographical correction is also beneficial.
- iii) Digital Assistants: To reduce inhuman needs, sophisticated enterprises today employ artificial intelligence technologies like characters, which are examples of digital assistants. The Avatar's complete absence of emotion gives them the capacity to make entirely rational decisions. Human emotions and moods are obstacles to decision-making, and machine intelligence can help. Repetitive tasks: Humans can generally perform one task at a time. Machines are better suited to multitasking and analysis than humans. The machine can alter speed and time, among its many settings, to adjust to their needs.

➤ *Disadvantage of AI technology*

The following are some major disadvantages of AI technology: [20, 43, 55]

- i) Expensive: AI launches require a significant financial outlay. The machine's intricate design makes maintenance and repairs incredibly economical. It takes an extended period for the R&D division to create a single AI system. Regular software upgrades are required for the AI machine. It takes more time and money to reinstall the system.

ii) No Human Copying: As AI technology gives robots the ability to execute a task more precisely and without bias, it relates to the insensitivity of human thought. When unidentified issues arise, robots may decide to report incorrect information.

iii) Experience does not improve: Experience can enhance human resources. However, experience cannot enhance computers that are outfitted with artificial intelligence technologies. They are unable to identify the type of person who works hard.

➤ Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming the pharmaceutical research and drug development landscape into a setting for superior speeds, accuracy, and efficiency. With this ability to synthesize complex datasets, AI enables researchers to move from methodologies dependent upon tradition to data-driven frameworks. Through the application of machine learning and deep learning principles, we are able to dramatically shorten the timeframe of drug research in a variety of process areas, such as target identification and candidate optimization. By using AI, we can not only shorten timelines, but also save costs and decrease the probabilities of failure. Examples of AI tools such as quantitative structure-activity relationship models and virtual screening have the potential to aid researchers through the early stages of research. AI will also greatly strengthen the clinical trial process in areas such as patient recruitment and patient monitoring. While data quality and ethical issues exist in its use in health research, the advent of explainable AI, and partnership between sectors have the potential to impact the success of its implementation. The potential health impact of less or possibly no human error and a more manageable timeframe would occur in addition to human knowledge, experience, knowledge, and skills; some may be optimistic about a future where health solutions are developed alongside AI and its combined capabilities with human-based knowledge and skills.

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